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Macroscopic and microscopic properties of fabric rubber composite

X.F. Yao*, Y.F. Dong

Applied Mechanics Laboratory, Department of Engineering Mechanics, Tsinghua University, Beijing, China. * Corresponding author (yxf@mail.tsinghua.edu.cn)

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Fabric rubber composite

Fig.1 The application of fabric rubber composite in the airplane

Fig.2 Complex fabric rubber composite and fabric structures

- **The complex fabric rubber composite material consists of silicone rubber as the matrix material and polyester fiber as the reinforcement material.**
- **The inner fabric is the reticulated fabric, which mainly plays the role of reinforcement.**
- **The surface fabric is densely distributed and mainly serves to resist abrasion.**

The material properties of fabric and rubber

Fig.3 The relationship between stress and strain of rubber material under different temperatures.

The hyperelastic constitutive model

$$W_R = C_{10}(\theta)(I_1 - 3) + C_{01}(\theta)(I_2 - 3) + \frac{1}{D_1(\theta)}(J - 1)^2$$

Fig.4 The relationship between fiber modulus and temperature

The relationship between the modulus of fiber material and temperature

$$E(T) = \frac{E_U + E_R}{2} - \frac{E_U - E_R}{2} \tanh [k(T - T')]$$

Inner reticulated fabric rubber composite

Fig.5: (a) The geometrical structure of the inner fabric. (b) Reticulated fabric rubber composite structure

The anisotropic hyperelastic model of the reticulated fabric rubber composite under different temperatures:

$$W = W_R + W_F + W_{\text{int}} = C_{10}(\theta)(I_1 - 3) + C_{01}(\theta)(I_2 - 3) + \frac{k_1(\theta)}{2k_2(\theta)} \sum_{j=4,6} \left[e^{k_2(\theta)(I_j - 1)^2} + \frac{k_2(\theta)}{4}(I_j - 1)^2 - 1 \right]$$

The nominal stress of the inner reticulated fabric rubber composite

$$T_1 = 2C_{10}(\theta)\lambda_1 + 2\frac{C_{01}}{\lambda_1}(\lambda_1^2\lambda_2^2 + \lambda_2^2\lambda_3^2 + \lambda_3^2\lambda_1^2 - \lambda_1^{-2}) + k_1(\theta) \cdot \lambda_1 \left[\frac{1}{2}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2) - 1 \right] \left[e^{k_2(\theta) \left[\frac{1}{2}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2) - 1 \right]^2} + \frac{1}{4} \right] + k_1(\theta) \cdot \lambda_1 \left[\frac{1}{2}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2) - 1 \right] \left[e^{k_2(\theta) \left[\frac{1}{2}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2) - 1 \right]^2} + \frac{1}{4} \right] - \frac{p}{\lambda_1}$$

$$T_2 = 2C_{10}(\theta)\lambda_2 + 2\frac{C_{01}}{\lambda_2}(\lambda_1^2\lambda_2^2 + \lambda_2^2\lambda_3^2 + \lambda_3^2\lambda_1^2 - \lambda_2^{-2}) + k_1(\theta) \cdot \lambda_2 \left[\frac{1}{2}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2) - 1 \right] \left[e^{k_2(\theta) \left[\frac{1}{2}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2) - 1 \right]^2} + \frac{1}{4} \right] + k_1(\theta) \cdot \lambda_2 \left[\frac{1}{2}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2) - 1 \right] \left[e^{k_2(\theta) \left[\frac{1}{2}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2) - 1 \right]^2} + \frac{1}{4} \right] - \frac{p}{\lambda_2}$$

$$T_3 = 2C_{10}(\theta)\lambda_3 + 2\frac{C_{01}}{\lambda_3}(\lambda_1^2\lambda_2^2 + \lambda_2^2\lambda_3^2 + \lambda_3^2\lambda_1^2 - \lambda_3^{-2}) - \frac{p}{\lambda_3}$$

Fig.6 The uniaxial tensile experimental results of the inner reticulated fabric rubber composite

Surface fabric rubber composite

Fig.7: (a) The physical map and geometrical model of front structure. (b) The physical map and geometrical model of back structure.

Fig.8 The forming process of RVE for the surface fabric rubber composite

Fig.9: Comparison of numerical simulation results and experimental results of vertical and transverse stress-strain relationship for surface fabric rubber composite: (a) vertical (b) transverse

Mechanical property of the complex fabric rubber composite

Fig.10: The distribution of different material and geometrical model (mm) of the complex fabric rubber composite.

Fig.11 Fabric rubber composite compression experiment under different temperatures

Fig.12 The numerical simulation results and experimental results of unit length load-displacement curves for the complex fabric rubber composite under different temperatures: (a) 25° C. (b) 50° C. (c) 70° C. (d) 90° C. (e) 110° C. (f) 130° C.

Thank you for your attention